

TWO-DIMENSIONAL AND TRANSIENT THERMAL MODEL OF THE CONTINUOUS TAPE LAYING PROCESS

Maria Skandali¹, K.M.B Jansen², Sotiris Koussios³, Jos Sinke⁴ and Rinze Benedictus⁵

¹Department of Structural Integrity and Composites, Technical University of Delft,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands
Email: M.Skandali@tudelft.nl web page: <http://staff.tudelft.nl/en/M.Skandali/>

²Department of Product Engineering, Technical University of Delft,
Landbergstraat 15, 2628CE Delft, The Netherlands
Email: k.m.b.jansen@tudelft.nl web page: <http://staff.tudelft.nl/en/K.m.b.Jansen/>

³Department of Structural Integrity and Composites, Technical University of Delft,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands
Email: S.Koussios@tudelft.nl web page: <http://staff.tudelft.nl/en/S.Koussios/>

⁴Department of Structural Integrity and Composites, Technical University of Delft,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands
Email: J.Sinke@tudelft.nl web page: <http://staff.tudelft.nl/en/J.Sinke/>

⁵Department of Structural Integrity and Composites, Technical University of Delft,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands
Email: R.Benedictus@tudelft.nl web page: <http://staff.tudelft.nl/en/R.Benedictus/>

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to simulate the two-dimensional, transient and continuous heat transfer during the thermoset Automated Tape Laying (ATL) process. The heat transfer analysis is coupled with a cure kinetics model of the thermoset prepreg tapes used for the process. Unlike most studies, the process is modelled in a Lagrangian framework and is based on the realistic boundary conditions of the ATL such as the stepwise laying down of the tapes. The model results provide information about the temperature values at any time and any location inside the thermoset composite tapes.

The temperature simulation results of the model were compared with experiments. Three layers of unidirectional prepreg tapes were laid down on an aluminium mould by the TU Delft ATL machine. The experimental results were obtained from thermocouples and pyrometers placed at various locations in the lay-up and on the robotic head, respectively.

The comparison between the numerical and experimental results generated three main findings. First, the pyrometer values and the thermocouple values provide insight into how important is the contact between the mould and the first layer. Secondly, the temperature fading out which was witnessed by the thermocouple measurements and could not entirely be captured by the model provided information about the influence of the heat transfer coefficients on the model predictions. Thirdly, the peak temperature magnitudes of the numerical predictions appeared to generally compare well with the experimental results. Overall, the code can be used for different parameter values such as different line speed, heated length and power of the heat source and, can predict the temperature distribution inside the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of composite materials in aerospace industry (A380 Flap Skin, the Boeing 777 empennage skin lay-up etc.) and the structural quality of those structures have been the focus of recent studies. Quality properties such as residual stresses or porosities are created during the manufacturing process. The inconsistency, if not the control, of the quality properties during manual processes can be minimized by the inclusion of automation at the manufacturing. Automation also promises for the control of parameters such as speed of lay-up, etc. Such an automated manufacturing process is the Automated Tape Laying.

ATL can make use of a robotic manipulator which lays down thermoset or thermoplastic prepreg tapes on a mould. The tapes are delivered to a roller which lays them down on the mould after applying pressure to assure compaction. Then, a heat source heats the interface point between the previous surface and the coming tape. Finally, the tape is cut and the process is repeated.

Many studies have been conducted on the heat transfer modelling of ATL. Most studies have focused on Eulerian description of the heat transfer mechanisms during ATL [1-7], while rather less have focused on the Lagrangian description of the same process [8, 9]. Beyeler and Guceri proposed a two-dimensional model of the heat transfer of thermoplastic laminates with the inclusion of crystallization kinetics [5]. Grove suggested a two-dimensional model which used a finite element mesh fixed at the moving head [1]. Neihad et al. also provided a two-dimensional model assuming that the temperature distribution influenced by the heat source remains unchanged with reference a fixed coordinate frame [2, 3]. Sarazzin and Springer developed a two-dimensional transient model based on the Lagrangian framework assuming that the tapes are instantaneously laid down [8]. Kim et al. demonstrated a two-dimensional Eulerian model by using a hot-gas heat source [4]. Sonmez and Hahn described the Eulerian approach of the ATL problem including crystallization and degradation studies [6, 7]. Hassan et al. posed a transient Lagrangian description of the ATL heat transfer using previous knowledge from filament winding models [9, 10]. Barasinski et al. investigated the effect of the interply thermal contact resistance [11].

According to the literature, there is little attention paid to the Lagrangian description of the ATL heat transfer problem and the fact that the layers are laid down following a stepwise pattern. In addition, most of the research on thermosets focuses on the use of infrared heaters so as to only increase the tackiness of the tapes despite the fact that higher temperatures can be beneficial [12].

The aim of this work is to model the two-dimensional and transient Lagrangian formulation of the ATL heat transfer process by using more heat than that of the conventional thermoset ATL. The tapes are also considered to be laid down in a stepwise interply function. In this approach, predictions of the temperature at more accurate time steps and positions inside the composite can be achieved. However, difficulties related to the different interfaces among the layers can be encountered. In the following sections the problem statement, the model, the model results and the conclusions are presented.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Figure 1 describes the geometry and the components of the domain of interest. The thermoset prepreg tape is delivered to an aluminum mould where is compressed by a roller which is moving at a constant speed. After 0.5[s], the roller stops and waits for 1.5 [s] for the infrared heater to turn on. During that stop of the roller, the tape remains in no contact with the previous surface (substrate). Next, the roller continues moving while the heater is still turned on. The infrared heater heats the bottom of the incoming tape at a maximum of 60-80 [° C] for 2.4 [s]. After 2.4[s], the roller stops again for 0.5 [s] while the knife cuts the tape. During the cutting time, the tape is again in no contact with the substrate. Then, the roller continues compacting the tape to the substrate until the end of the tape course (302[mm]). Since the thickness of the prepreg is much smaller than its width and length, the problem becomes two-dimensional by neglecting the edge effects.

Figure 1: Geometry of the ATL problem and thermocouple positions

Figure 2: Head parts and pyrometer position

3 EXPERIMENTAL

In order to validate the model, three-layered composite laminates were manufactured by the ATL machine of TU Delft laboratory. The head assembly is displayed at Figure 2. The incoming prepreg tape is delivered to the aluminum mould surface. At one side of the head an infrared pyrometer is installed to measure the temperature of the bottom surface of the incoming prepreg.

Thermocouple positions		x ₁ axis	x ₂ axis
A1	[mm]	150	2.3
B1	[mm]	160	2.445
B2	[mm]	194	2.445
C1	[mm]	113	2.59
C2	[mm]	183	2.59

Table 1: Thermocouple positions

To measure the temperature distribution inside the composite, A1,B1,B2,C1,C2 thermocouples were embedded at five different locations within the heated area of the tape. Thermocouple A1 was placed at the interface “mould -first layer”, B1, B2 at the interface “first –second layer” and C1,C2 at the interface “second- third layer” as shown in Figure 1 and Table 1. The thermocouples were connected to a data acquisition system and the digital signals were registered by a computer.

The ATL used HexPly® 913C-HTA epoxy, carbon fiber unidirectional prepreg tapes and worked under specific parameter settings. The uncured prepreg was 50 [mm] wide and 0.145 [mm] thick and the three-layered composite was laid onto a 2.3 [mm] flat aluminum mould. The chosen lay-up speed was 50 [mm/sec], the heated length 140 [mm], the heat flux was estimated as 2.63E5 W/m² and the total length of the tape 302[mm].

4 NUMERICAL

In order to study the heat transfer problem, numerical simulations were performed. The thermoset prepreg was taken to be a homogeneous anisotropic material and the mould was assumed to have the same width and length as the incoming tapes (Figure 1). At each Δt a Δl of tape is laid next to the previous Δl of tape while the speed of the head follows the expression: $\Delta l/\Delta t$.

The goal of this heat transfer study is to find the temperature distribution as a function of time and space to predict the temperature at any location and any time inside the composite material. The governing equation for the description of the problem is based on the transient heat conduction equation:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(k_{11} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_1} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(k_{22} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_2} \right) - \dot{Q}_1 - \dot{Q}_2 \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}_1 = \rho_m v_m \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right) H_R \quad (2)$$

where C_p is the specific heat, T is the temperature, \dot{Q}_1 is the rate of heat generated per unit volume due to exothermic chemical reactions that occur during the resin cure, ρ_m is the resin density, v_m is

the resin volume fraction, $\frac{da}{dt}$ is rate of degree of cure, H_R is the ultimate heat of reaction, \dot{Q}_2 is the rate of energy supplied to a unit volume of the prepreg tape by the heat source, x_1, x_2 , are the inertia coordinates with x_1 representing the direction parallel to the fibres direction and x_2 the transverse direction (Figure 1) and k_{11}, k_{22} represent the thermal conductivities at the coordinate system which coincide with the the longitudinal and transverse material thermal conductivities, respectively. The material properties of the prepreg and the mould are presented in Table 2.

The boundary conditions are based on the fact that the layers are laid down following a stepwise function which proposes the use of a stepwise contact conductive boundary at each interface contributing with the heat flux boundary:

Engineering constant		Prepreg	Aluminium Mould
Thickness	[mm]	0.145	2.3
Fibre volume fraction	[-]	0.60	-
Density	[Kg/m ³]	1559	2700
Specific heat	[J/mol/K]	1339	900
Longitudinal thermal conductivity	[W/m/K]	3.67	200
Transverse thermal conductivity	[W/m/K]	0.65	200
Initial degree[13]		0	

Table 2:Prepreg and mould material properties

$$\text{Heat flux boundary condition : } -\mathbf{k}_{ij} \left(-\mathbf{n}_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) = \dot{Q}_2, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Contact boundary condition: } -\mathbf{k}_{ij} \left(-\mathbf{n}_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) = h_c (T_p - T) \quad (4)$$

where, \mathbf{k}_{ij} , h_c, T and T_p are the diagonal thermal conductivity matrix, the contact heat transfer coefficient, the temperature of the layer and the temperature of the previous surface in contact, respectively.

The top surface of each layer and the top surface of the mold is assumed to be exposed to heat transfer

$$\text{due to convection : } -\mathbf{k}_{ij} \left(-\mathbf{n}_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) = h (T_\infty - T) \quad (5)$$

The edges of each layer, the bottom of the mould and the edges of the mould are assumed insulated. That is:

$$-\mathbf{k}_{ij} \left(-\mathbf{n}_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where h is the heat transfer coefficient for convection, T_∞ is the ambient temperature and \mathbf{n}_i is the outward to the surface unit vector. The convection heat transfer coefficient was here assumed to be $900 \text{ [W/m}^2 \text{ /}^\circ\text{C]}$.

Engineering constant		Prepreg
k_0	[1/s]	218000000
E_a	[kJ/mol]	80.570
H_R	[kJ/kg]	530.769
R	[J/mol/K]	8.314
m	[-]	0.568
n	[-]	1.903

Table 3: Parameters of the cure kinetics model

When this thermoset prepreg material tapes are heated above $80\text{-}120 \text{ [}^\circ\text{C]}$, an exothermal reaction is initiated. The exothermal reaction generates heat inside the thermoset material which is included in \dot{Q}_1 (Equation 1). The heat generation term follows a one dimensional n th order formulation[13]. That is:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (7)$$

where k_0 , E_a , R , T , α , m , n are the pre-exponential factor, the activation energy, the universal gas constant, the absolute temperature, the degree of cure and the constants, respectively (Table 3)[13].

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Experimental results

The experiment was conducted with three layers of 302 [mm] tape. The deposition of the layers A, B, C occurred within the time ranges $[37.5 \text{ } 60] \text{ [s]}$, $[60 \text{ } 82] \text{ [s]}$ and $[82 \text{ } 90] \text{ [s]}$, respectively, with a time step of 0.5 [s] . Each layer was initially in room temperature and was later heated from the bottom surface for 2.4 [s] (red line in Figure 3). This heating time corresponds to the so called heated length of each tape which here is 140 [mm] . At different times the roller either moved or stopped (stop1: when the heater is turned on, stop2: at cutting time of the cut unit) which determined the activation or deactivation of the contact conductive boundary among the layers (blue line in Figure 3).

Figure 3:a) Temperature plotted with time from five thermocouples b) Temperature plotted with time from the pyrometer (positions on the tape also referred by the green lines) –Heater (red) and contact functions (blue) are plotted for both sensor types

Based on Figure 3a, all the thermocouples experienced different temperature maximum depending on the location of the thermocouple within the heated length. While the B1,B2 C1,C2 maximum temperatures occurred at the times that the heater was turned on, the A1 thermocouple experienced its temperature peak at almost the end of the heating zone. This indicated how differently the interface “mould -first layer” can behave because it connects two different materials.

The temperature at the layer interfaces were also measured by a pyrometer (Figure 3b) placed on the head as is shown at Figure 2. The pyrometer measurements provide information about the temperature distribution while the tape is being laid down which means that neither the position (green lines in Figure 3b) nor the time was fixed during the measurement. All the pyrometer points were along a cut-line across the bottom of each layer of tape (Figure 2) which reached a maximum of 60-80 [°C] before the laying down of it on the substrate. All the peak temperatures from the pyrometer occurred within the heating time.

5.2 Numerical results

The solution of the numerical problem was obtained by a transient finite element method in Comsol which takes into account the continuous motion of the ATL head following a set of fixed material particles (Lagrangian approach). The numerical steps were : a) construct a finite element mesh of both the mould and the composite tapes, b) create the geometries to apply the boundary conditions, c) at each time step add a new piece of tape and calculate the temperature, e) use the temperature at the first step as an initial temperature of the initial degree of cure.

Numerical calculations were executed using the model of this study in order to make a comparison with the thermocouple measurements. Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6a present the temperature as a function of time for the five thermocouples. The model seems to slightly overpredict the temperature maximum of the “mould-first layer” interface as it is shown by the first peak of thermocouple A1 (Figure 6a, solid stars). B1,B2,C1,C2 show ,however, the model underprediction of the temperatures at the other two interfaces (Figure 4 and Figure 5). This again indicates the different behaviour of the first interface mould-first layer. Furthermore, the not exactly followed cooling down of the composite can be due to the estimated values of the convection heat transfer coefficient.

The pyrometer values were also compared with numerical calculations. Figure 6b illustrates the temperature as a function of both time and location as the pyrometer measurements are taken while the head is moving. Each of the three different peaks represent the temperature experience of each of the three tapes. Although the general shape of the temperature profile is predicted quite well for the third layer, the temperatures of the interface “mould -first layer” and “first -second layer” are underpredicted by the model. The temperature mismatch can be due to the fact that the times at which the experimental measurements are taken do not precisely correspond to the equivalent times in the model as the response times of the sensors are in [s] and any change occurs in [ms].

6 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical and experimental heat transfer study of was conducted in this work. The experimental results are in good agreement with the numerical predictions for the peak temperatures and the cooling down of each layer.

The general outcome of the study showed that the time-dependence of the problem increases the complexity of it. According to A1 thermocouple measurement the model has a delayed response time for the mould-first layer interface (Figure 6a) which suggests that the predicted pyrometer values for the same interface will correspond to different times than the experimental ones. This means lower temperature predictions for the pyrometer but higher for the thermocouple A1 for the first interface.

a)

b)

Figure 4:a) Temperature plotted with time from B1 thermocouple and comparison with numerical results, b) Temperature plotted with time from B2 thermocouple and comparison with numerical results

a)

b)

Figure 5: a) Temperature plotted with time from C1 thermocouple and comparison with numerical results, b) Temperature plotted with time from C2 thermocouple and comparison with numerical results

a)

b)

Figure 6:a) Temperature plotted with time from A1 thermocouple and comparison with numerical results, b)Temperature plotted with time from pyrometer experiment and comparison with numerical results (positions on the tape also referred by green lines)

Similarly the second interface model predictions for the pyrometer are expected to continue to underpredict the experimental pyrometer values and thermocouple values (Figure 4 and Figure 6b). Finally according to the C thermocouples both the thermocouple and pyrometer measurements of the third interface are expected to be underpredicted by the model which is true for the thermocouples and unexpectedly false for the pyrometer (Figure 5 and Figure 6b). All the temperature mismatches can be fully explained by the fact that the time-dependency of the problem is based on changes of temperatures in [ms] and this can cause difficulties in synchronizing the sensors response times of [s] with the simulations.

Future studies are recommended for the assessment of the influence of the response times of the sensors and the estimated heat transfer coefficients on the temperature predictions of the model. The next steps towards this direction will be a) the repetition of the experiments for longer length of tape but at the same time keeping the same heated length ratio so that the time range among each change (heater on, heater off) is more than a few seconds and b) the change of the response time settings of the sensors from seconds to milliseconds. This approach will provide more precise control of when each change occurs and whether the two sensors are well synchronized or not for more accurate model inputs for each event.

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